

Climatological analysis of solar and wind energy in Germany using the Grosswetterlagen classification

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ABSTRACT

Solar and wind energy play an important role in current and future energy supply in Germany and Europe. The production of renewable energy highly depends on weather conditions resulting in an increasing impact of meteorological fluctuations on energy production. Here, climatological data of solar radiation and wind speed are used to simulate hourly capacity factors for solar and wind energy for Germany from 1995 to 2015. Using renewable energy production data for 2015 these data are converted into time series of generated electrical power. Events with very low energy production, i.e., shortfall events, have been identified and related to large-scale weather regimes over Europe.

In Germany, on average about twice as much electrical energy is generated from wind compared to solar radiation; in addition there is a distinct annual cycle with an equal share of generated energy during summer and a 70/30% wind/solar share in winter. There is an unambiguous dependency of wind and solar energy production on weather regimes. Shortfall events in Germany only occur in winter, often associated with a high pressure system over Central Europe. During this weather regime, the renewable energy potential in Northern and Southeastern Europe is above average, possibly allowing to balance shortfall events in Germany.

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1. Introduction

Conventional fossil energy sources, like coal and oil, are a major source of carbon dioxide emission and thereby a significant driver of climate change [1]. Anthropogenic climate change can be therefore mitigated by developing an energy system with an increase share of non-fossil technologies [1]. In such mitigation scenarios, renewable energies, like solar and wind energy, play an important role in shaping the current and future energy supply. In the European Union, 80% of new installed capacity is based on renewable energies; in particular the onshore and offshore wind energy installations are growing and might become a main energy source after 2030 [2]. On the global scale, solar energy might become the largest single source of energy in 2040 (with a 40% share of renewable energies), due to strong deployment of photovoltaic (PV) power plants especially in China and India [2,3].

Although specific electrical devices nowadays have become more efficient in using electricity, the demand for electricity is expected to increase due to the increase in population with access to electrical power. In addition the development of the transport and heating sector (e.g., by application of heat pumps) towards electrification will enhance the consumption of electrical power.

The enhanced generation of electrical energy from renewable energy sources, especially solar radiation and wind, is important for a sustainable future energy supply. However, in contrast to conventional sources of energy, the availability of renewable energy sources is strongly linked to the meteorological conditions, i.e., the amount of solar radiation and wind, and, hence, temporally and spatially much more variable. In addition, the increase in electrical mobility and electrical heating enhances the impact of the weather conditions on the demand for electricity. The current energy system needs to be adjusted to cope with the increasing (and fluctuating) production of electrical energy from renewable sources as well as with weather-dependent demands to maintain its reliability and stability [4].

Potential balancing effects of wind and solar energy generation

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have been assessed for some countries and regions, e.g., Kaspar et al. [5], Schindler et al. [6] (Germany); Sterl et al. [7] (West Africa); Liu et al. [8] (China); Hoicka and Rowlands [9] (Ontario, Canada); Santos-Alamillos et al. [10]; Jerez et al. [11] (Iberia Peninsula); Bett and Thornton [12] (Britain); Miglietta et al. [13] (Europe). Some of these studies focus purely on the meteorological parameters (i.e., solar radiation, wind speed) and their interrelations; other studies estimate the electrical energy generated from solar radiation and wind speed based on assumptions with different complexity and realism (see Engeland et al. [14] for a comprehensive literature review). One of the common conclusions of those studies is that the complementarity of wind and solar energy is enhanced when large regions and long time periods are considered.

Using new concepts of energy system models, balancing the local variability of varying renewable energy generation in the electrical energy system is investigated. These models consider the production and the demand of electrical energy based on historical data and can assess the impacts of different scenarios, e.g., for the transmission through power grids or local storage of electrical energy. Heide et al. [15,16] examined a simplified European power system which relies mostly on renewable energies, in terms of storage requirements and balancing needs. They concluded that the minimum need of required energy storage occurs at an optimal mix of about 60% wind and 40% solar power generation for a 100% renewable energy scenario. Schlachtberger et al. [17] and Brown et al. [18] studied the benefits of an European cooperation in terms of energy distribution and provided ways to an European renewable energy network. They investigated concepts for balancing the variability of solar and wind energy and found that, on a continental scale, the fluctuations of energy can be balanced with an electricity transmission grid, whereas storage capabilities, like batteries, help balance on the local scale.

Typical weather patterns have been defined to reduce the complexity of the meteorological variability and to allow the identification of reoccurring patterns in the weather system. These patterns are typically defined by their synoptic meteorological patterns (e.g., regional scale pressure and temperature fields and resulting surface flows) and are grouped in weather classifications. While many different weather classifications already exist (e.g. Ref. [19–22]), the so-called Grosswetterlagen classification based on [23] and revised by Hess and Brezowsky in 1950/51 (see Refs. [24]) is well suited to classify the synoptic situation in Central Europe with 29 different weather types. Grams et al. [25] used a new classification of seven weather regimes, which focus on the large-scale flow variability, to identify European regions with balancing wind capacities to reduce the variability of generated wind energy in a future renewable energy system. An interesting new approach is the so-called ‘targeted circulation types’ (TCT) that are derived from the power system’s response (e.g., production and demand) to meteorological data [26].

This study is an extension of the study by Kaspar et al. [5], where the authors analysed balancing effects of solar and wind energy for Germany and Europe using with simplified assumptions and neglecting real production data. Here, we use electricity production data of 2015 to calibrate our simulation of the generated wind and solar energy and to derive a realistic estimate of the generated wind and solar electrical energy from 1995 to 2015 (assuming the installed systems as of 2015). To address potentially problematic situations for the electrical energy system in Germany, i.e., a shortfall in renewable energy production over a longer time period, we focus on time periods (up to 120 h) with very low wind and solar energy production and determine the weather regimes associated with them. European regions with the potential to balance the low renewable energy generation in Germany under these conditions are identified.

Following the methodology of the study from Kaspar et al. [5] we are also using the satellite-based data record CM SAF SARAH-2.1 (available from 1983 to 2017) and the 116 m wind speed (1995–2015) of the regional reanalysis COSMO-REA6 to estimate the capacity factors (CFs) for solar and wind energy, respectively. The CFs describe the actual power output relative to the installed capacity (value range between 0 and 1). Using information of the installed and actual produced energy in Germany for 2015 [27], the simulated CFs are converted into energy production, to result in a time series of potential solar, wind, and total renewable energy produced from 1995 to 2015 in Germany assuming the renewable energy installations of 2015 (Section 3). Time periods with particularly low renewable energy production and their associated weather patterns are identified and discussed (Section 4).

2. Data

This chapter describes the datasets used in this study based on satellite observations, reanalysis, actual and simulated energy data and the Grosswetterlagen classification. Table 1 summarizes the datasets used in this work.

2.1. Satellite data: CM SAF SARAH-2.1

The satellite-based dataset used in this study is the Solar Surface Radiation Heliosat (SARAH-2.1) data record [28,29] provided by the EUMETSAT Satellite Application Facility on Climate Monitoring (CM SAF) based on observations from the geostationary Meteosat satellites with a spatial coverage from about 65 °N to 65 °S. It includes global and direct radiation with a grid spacing of $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ and a temporal resolution of 30 min from 1983 to 2017 and is therefore appropriate for a climatological analysis.

For the generation of a consistent and long-term climate data record, a specific climate algorithm, the MAGIC SOL approach, was applied. One part of the algorithm is the Heliosat method [30,31] which calculates the effective cloud albedo (CAL). The second part of the MAGIC SOL approach is the SPEC MAGIC (Mesoscale Atmosphere Global Irradiance Code) clear sky model [32] which calculates the global and direct solar radiation at ground-level. Considering CAL then enables the calculation of all-sky radiances. One output parameter is the surface incoming radiation (SIS), which is the irradiance reaching the horizontal plane at the Earth surface in the visible spectrum. Whereas SID is the solar incoming direct radiation [33]. SIS and SID are either used to simulate solar energy production.

SARAH-2.1 is validated in detail [34], homogeneous [35] and available via the CM SAF web user interface [36]. The product is widely used for climate analysis (e.g. Ref. [29]), climate modeling (e.g. Ref. [37]), and renewable energies (e.g., Ref. [38–40]).

2.2. Reanalysis data: COSMO-REA6

The regional reanalysis COSMO-REA6 [41] was developed at the Hans-Ertel-Center for Weather Research (HERZ) in a cooperation of the Universities of Bonn and Cologne and Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD; Germany’s national meteorological service) [42]. It has a grid spacing of 6 km \times 6 km and an hourly temporal resolution. The data used in this study covers the time period 1995 to 2015. The model covers Europe, i.e., the COORDINATED Regional climate Downscaling Experiment) EUR-11 domain, from about 27 °N to 71 °N and 22 °W to 44 °E. The data of COSMO-REA6 is quality-checked, as it is shown in Kaiser-Weiss et al. [43]; Borsche et al. [44]; Kaiser-Weiss et al. [45] and also used for applications in the energy sector [46–48] and therefore appropriate for this study (for a review of evaluation results and energy applications, see

Ref. [42]). The meteorological parameters used here are the 2 m temperature and the wind speed in 116 m. 116 m corresponds to a typical hub height of a wind turbine and is used for calculating the wind CF according to the method of Kaspar et al. [5] described further in Section 3.2. The 2 m-temperature is used for calculating the solar CF (Section 3.1). Further parameters are publicly available via DWD/HERZ [49].

2.3. Energy data

2.3.1. Open Power System Data

For the validation and the scaling of the simulated CF based on satellite and reanalysis data, a dataset of actual energy output from solar and wind plants is needed. In this study the database is an open source platform called “Open Power System Data” [27]. OPSD provides a collection of datasets from different sources like Bundesnetzagentur or ENTSO-E (European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity) Data Portal for 37 European countries. The datasets of interest for this study are the time series of installed solar and wind capacity, their actual power production and the locations of the individual power plants. More information can be found in Wiese et al. [50].

2.3.2. EMHIREs datasets

The EMHIREs (European Meteorological derived HIGH RESolution generation time series for present and future scenarios) datasets contain simulated solar and wind power generation for Europe derived from meteorological data and is provided by the Joint Research Center (JRC). Both datasets are available from 1986 to 2015 on an hourly basis and include the capacity factors of EU-28 countries, Norway, Switzerland and non EU countries of the Western Balkans [51]. The wind speed data used to generate the EMHIREs time series is based on the MERRA global reanalysis (Modern Era Retrospective-Analysis for Research and Applications) [52]. The radiation data used in EMHIREs is the CM SAF SARAH data record [38], the predecessor of the SARAH-2.1 used in this study. The EMHIREs time series is validated with TSO (Transmission System Operators) data containing the actual solar and wind power generation series for 2015 to evaluate systematic errors of the time series. EMHIREs solar and wind power time series are normalized to the ENTSO-E annual production statistics reported.

In this study the time series of the capacity factors for each

European country are used to analyse potential balancing effects of energy generation across Europe. Further information on the generation of the time series, as well as the EMHIREs data itself can be found in Gonzalez-Aparicio et al. [38,51].

2.4. Grosswetterlagen

The Grosswetterlagen (GWL) classification is a set of 29 large-scale European weather patterns, originally described by Ref. [53] and which has been classified manually by various synoptic meteorologists back to 1881 and up to the present day at the DWD. The GWLs used in this study are based on an improved and updated version of the automatic-objective GWL classification method of James [54]. This method classifies daily synoptic patterns via spatial correlation coefficients against climatological mean patterns for each GWL. This procedure uses four meteorological fields (mean-sea-level pressure, 500 hPa geopotential height, 500–1000 hPa geopotential thickness and the total precipitable water column), derived from ECMWF ERA40 reanalyses from 1958 to 1978 and ERA-Interim reanalyses from 1979 onwards. The resulting daily classification is temporally filtered with a low-pass filter to remove all single day events and the majority of two day events. The domain is centered on Central Europe, but also takes the circulation over the rest of Europe and the North-East Atlantic into account. Due to the automatic-objective classification method the resulting GWL catalogue is much more homogeneous and consistent over time than the manually classified Hess and Brezowsky GWL series. The GWLs are used in this study to analyse the meteorological situations associated with low energy production days. A full list of the 29 GWL names can be found in James [54].

3. Methodology

The solar and wind capacity factors (CFs) are important components in this study and are explained in Section 3.1, and 3.2 respectively. Section 3.3 shows the spatial averaging of solar and wind CFs. Its calibration with actual energy production data is presented in Section 3.4.

3.1. Solar capacity factor

For the estimation of the solar capacity factor the solar radiation

Table 1

Overview of the datasets used in this study with the parameter, including their spatial and temporal resolution in column 1–6. The last two columns describe the application in this study and the related chapter number.

Dataset	Parameter	Temporal		Spatial		Application	Chapter number
		Coverage	Resolution	Coverage	Resolution		
SARAH - 2.1	SIS [W/m ²], SID [W/m ²]	1983 –2017	30 min	65 °N to 65 °S, 65 °W to 65 °E	0.05° × 0.05°	solar CF calculation	2.1, 3.1
COSMO - REA6	116 m wind speed [m/s], 2 m-temperature [K]	1995 –2015	hourly	27 °N to 71 °N, 22 °W to 44 °E	6 km × 6 km	wind CF calculation, solar CF calculation	2.2, 3.1, 3.2
OPSD	CF [%], gen. Energy [GWh], solar/wind power installations [MW]	status: 2015	hourly	Europe	–	actual energy data to calibrate the calculated CF	2.3.1, 3.3, 3.4
Generated Dataset	CF [%], gen. Energy [GWh]	1995 –2015	hourly	Germany	0.05° × 0.05°	solar and wind CF as the basis for whole data analysis	3, 4.1–4.5
EMHIREs	CF [%]	1995 –2015	hourly	Europe	country-wise	CF of European countries for showing balancing effects	2.3.2, 4.6
GWL		1958 - today	6-hourly	Europe	–	meteorological explanation of different shortfall scenarios	2.4, 4.3–4.6

that reaches the PV cell as well as the efficiency of the PV cell to convert the solar radiation into electrical power are required.

To optimize the available solar radiation and the energy yield, solar energy installation are tilted, typically, towards south, i.e., the direction of maximum solar radiation. In Germany, PV installations are often installed on roofs that already have a predefined orientation. For a realistic simulation of the generated solar power from PV installations in Germany, an assumption on the orientation of the PV cells has to be made. In this study we use the probabilistic approach by Saint-Drenan et al. [55,56] that assumes a weighted distribution of different orientations (described by the inclination and the azimuth angles of the PV systems).

Based on data from 35 000 solar plants, Saint-Drenan et al. [56] found an average inclination angle of 20.6° (μ_γ), which is assumed to be representative for all solar plants in Germany. The azimuth angle has been found to be centered in southern orientation ($\mu_\alpha = 180^\circ$) as expected. The values for the standard deviations σ_α^2 and σ_γ^2 are found to be 19.3° and 10.8° respectively. For the technical implementation of the variability of the orientation of the PV modules we use a set of 9 different module orientations, i.e., 3 inclination and 3 azimuth angles, and derive the appropriate weights (normalized to unity) for those combinations based on the Gaussian distributions (Equation (1), see also Saint-Drenan et al. [56] for further details of the technical implementation). The derived weights for the 9 orientations used here are shown in Table 2.

$$w_i(\alpha_i, \gamma_i) = \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \pi \cdot \sigma_\alpha^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\alpha_i - \mu_\alpha)^2}{2 \cdot \sigma_\alpha^2}\right) \right] \cdot \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{2 \cdot \pi \cdot \sigma_\gamma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\gamma_i - \mu_\gamma)^2}{2 \cdot \sigma_\gamma^2}\right) \right] \quad (1)$$

The incident solar energy on a tilted PV system, G , depends on the orientation of the PV cell, the solar geometry, as well as on the atmospheric optical properties, i.e, whether a cloud is impacting the direct solar radiation, and can be estimated from the horizontal direct and the diffuse radiation. Here we use the global and direct solar radiation data from the SARA-2.1 data set at a temporal resolution of 30 min to estimate the incident solar radiation for each of the 9 orientations of PV cells. The estimation of the solar radiation on a tilted plane is conducted with the R-package “solar” by Lamigueiro [57].

Subsequently, the solar capacity factor is estimated using the solar radiation on the tilted PV cell and the temperature of the cell based on the work by Huld et al. [58]:

$$CF(G, T_{mod}) = P_{STC} \cdot \frac{G}{G_{STC}} \cdot \eta_{rel}(G', T') \quad (2)$$

The CF is described as a function of G , the radiation on the tilted surface, and T_{mod} , the temperature of the solar panel; the efficiency of a solar panel under Standard Test Conditions (STC), P_{STC} , is part of the technical description of solar cells and set to 1000 W in our case. Standard Test Conditions are defined as a solar radiation at the PV cell of 1000 $\frac{W}{m^2}$ and a temperature of the PV module of $T_{mod,STC} = 25^\circ C$. The relative efficiency, η_{rel} , describes the efficiency of the PV module under different conditions of temperature and radiation relative to the STC:

$$\eta_{rel}(G', T') = 1 + k_1 \ln G' + k_2 (\ln G')^2 + T' (k_3 + k_4 \ln G' + k_5 (\ln G')^2) + k_6 T'^2 \quad (3)$$

with

$$T' = T_{mod} - T_{mod,STC} \quad (4)$$

$$G' = \frac{G}{G_{STC}} \quad (5)$$

The values for the coefficients k_1 to k_6 used here are taken from Huld and Amillo [59] for crystalline silicon (c-Si).

The temperature of the module is estimated from the ambient temperature at 2 m, T_{amb} , and the effect of solar radiation on the module temperature:

$$T_{mod} = T_{amb} + c_T \cdot G \quad (6)$$

The temperature coefficient c_T describes how the panel is heated up depending on radiation and is set to 0.025 $^\circ C \frac{m^2}{W}$ [39,58].

Finally, the average solar capacity factor for each grid cell (a total of 241 × 201 in Germany) and hour is derived as the weighted mean of the solar CF using the weights as provided in Table 2.

3.2. Wind capacity factor

The energy production of a wind turbine depends on the wind speed and is described by the power curve (Fig. 1).

The cut-in wind speed v_{cut_in} is the wind speed at which the wind turbine starts to generate power. The curve follows the theoretical assumption of $P_v \propto v^3$ until the rated output is reached. The rated power output describes the maximum power output of a wind turbine and is given by Equation (7) including the air density ρ , the efficiency η_v and the area of a rotor blades with radius R . The corresponding wind speed v_{rated} is the maximum level of the wind turbine as a power generator, limited by its installed capacity (P_{rated}). For higher wind speeds the power output can only be as high as the rated generated power. If the wind speed increases further the wind turbine might be damaged due to high force effects on the rotor blades. The wind turbines are switched off at a certain wind speed to prevent such impacts. This so-called cut-out wind speed v_{cut_out} is about 25 m/s.

$$P_{rated} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \eta_v \pi R^2 v_{rated}^3 \quad (7)$$

$$P_v = \begin{cases} 0, & v < v_{cut_in} \\ P_{rated} \left(\frac{v}{v_{rated}}\right)^3, & v_{cut_in} \leq v \leq v_{rated} \\ P_{rated}, & v_{rated} \leq v \leq v_{cut_out} \\ 0, & v > v_{cut_out} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In this study the capacity factor is calculated which is described

Table 2
The assumed inclination (μ_γ) and azimuth (μ_α) angles [°] used for calculating the solar CF as well as the corresponding weighting factor w_i .

μ_γ/μ_α	w_i	μ_γ/μ_α	w_i	μ_γ/μ_α	w_i
30/170	0.084	30/180	0.136	30/190	0.095
20/170	0.100	20/180	0.155	20/190	0.109
10/170	0.084	10/180	0.136	10/190	0.095

by the ratio of the generated power and the installed capacity (Equation (9)) (which means there are no further parameters which have to be calculated first).

$$CF_v = \frac{P_v}{P_{rated}} = \frac{\text{generated power}}{\text{installed capacity}} \quad (9)$$

The wind capacity factors are based on the method described in Kaspar et al. [5]. The calculation is based on the R package “bReeze” by Graul, C. and Poppinga, C. [60], which provides functions to analyse wind data and estimate potential energy production of wind turbines. The assumed power curve is the “Enercon_E126_7.5 MW” [61] with $v_{cut_in} = 3 \frac{m}{s}$, $v_{rated} = 16 \frac{m}{s}$ and $v_{cut_out} = 25 \frac{m}{s}$.

Input data for this study is the 116 m-wind speed based on the COSMO-REA6 (Section 2.2). The calculation of the wind capacity factor is done for each gridpoint in Germany separately for offshore and onshore. The height of the assumed wind turbine is about 116 m (4th model level above ground for wind speed [44]). The calculation is based on the direct model output for that level, so no vertical interpolation was done. The temporal resolution is hourly. The offshore region covers the Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) for Germany.

3.3. Weighted spatial averaging

This subsection describes the data processing of the time series from the spatially resolved capacity factors to the energy production in a given region, i.e. Germany (D) (see Equation (10)). Each capacity factor for each grid point and timestep in Germany is multiplied by the installed capacity per grid, to account for the unequal distribution of solar plants (Fig. 2).

More than 1.56 million solar plants [27] were installed in Germany in 2015, with a higher density in southern than in northern Germany. Some huge solar farms with up to 200 MW installed capacity each exist in the eastern part of Germany, but are distributed more sparsely. After dividing each gridcell by the installed capacity of 2015 (38 990 MW) the spatial sum for Germany is calculated resulting in a time series of solar capacity factors.

$$CF_D(t) = \frac{1}{\text{installed capacity [MW]}(2015)} \sum_{i,j} CF(i, j, t) \cdot \text{installed capacity [MW]}(i, j, 2015) \quad (10)$$

Fig. 1. The used power curve “Enercon_E126_7.5 MW” with the cut-in (v_{cut_in}), the cut-out wind speed (v_{cut_out}) and the wind speed at the maximum power output (v_{rated}).

The time series for wind was calculated in a similar manner, also considering the actual distribution of wind plants in Germany for the year 2015 (Fig. 3). A total of 24 442 wind plants or wind parks were installed in 2015, including 27 offshore wind parks, with a total installed capacity of 41 326 MW [27].

3.4. Calibration of simulated capacity factors

This section shows the comparison of the simulated solar and wind CFs with the actual produced energy based on the dataset of OPSD. For analysing shortfall events the sum of solar and wind energy production is of interest, while the calculated solar and wind CFs cannot be simply added up. The CFs are converted into produced energy with:

$$\text{generated power} = CF \cdot \text{installed capacity (2015)} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 4 presents the correlation of hourly simulated solar CFs with the solar energy production as the percentage of the installed capacity (y-axis on the left-hand side) and the generated solar energy (y-axis on the right-hand side; based on OPSD in orange). The correlation considers the installed capacity of the solar plants per gridcell, which is the weighted spatial average from above. With consideration of the installed capacity of the solar plants the correlation on an hourly basis is around 99%. A linear fit (in line with [56]) is used to correct the general overestimation of the simulated data (red) with a calibration coefficient of 0.8 (based on the slope of the uncorrected data). This overestimation can be explained by some effects that are not considered in the calculation, like losses of energy by transferring energy in an electricity system and shading effects (by dust [62] or snow on solar panels or by trees and hills).

The calibration of the wind CFs is employed in a similar manner, but for a better comparison with the solar CFs the gridsize of the wind CFs of $0.055^\circ \times 0.055^\circ$ (6 km \times 6 km) is matched with the gridsize of the solar CFs of $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ (5 km \times 5 km). An offshore share of 8% is assumed (Section 2.3). Fig. 5 presents a correlation of the hourly simulated wind CFs and the produced wind energy as the percentage of the installed capacity (y-axis on the left-hand side) and the produced wind energy (y-axis on the right-hand side; based on OPSD in light blue). Some effects, like transmission losses or the shut-down of wind plants at high wind speeds to avoid overproduction or power deficits due to turbine wakes [63,64] are not considered in the calculation of the wind CFs which might be an explanation for the overestimation of these. A linear fit is used to correct the overestimated data with a calibration coefficient of 0.82 (blue). Both linear fits for 2015 are applied to all other years considered.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Climatological mean

Fig. 6 shows the distribution of the climatological (1995–2015) solar capacity factor based on SARA-2.1 30-min SIS and SID data. An angle distribution is assumed where the centered inclination angle is 20.6° and the azimuth angle is in southward orientation (180°). Consistent with the surface radiation, lower CF in northern Germany and higher ones in the south can be recognised. The CF varies spatially between 10% and 14%. This is consistent to the mean annual solar CF for Germany based on MERRA2 (12.4%) and SARA (11.5%) [39].

Fig. 7 shows the distribution of the climatological wind capacity factor based on the hourly 116 m wind speed of the regional reanalysis COSMO-REA6 data record. Lower CFs in southern Germany and higher ones in the north can be recognised. The CF varies

Electrical Capacity of Solar Plants per Gridcell in Germany, 2015

Fig. 2. Spatial distribution of the sum of installed photovoltaic capacity per gridcell in Germany in 2015.

between 5% and 50%. The highest wind CFs are mainly seen in the offshore regions in the North and Baltic Sea. These values correspond to the mean wind CF for Germany of 19.5% found by Staffell and Pfenninger [65] considering the time series from 1995 to 2015 based on MERRA.

4.2. Time series analysis

This section presents the results of the analysis of the energy

Electrical Capacity of Wind Plants per Gridcell in Germany, 2015

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of the sum of installed wind capacity per gridcell in Germany in 2015.

Correlation of simulated CF and OPSD, 2015 Germany, Hourly Data, Weighted Spatial Average

Fig. 4. Correlation of the hourly simulated CFs (based on CM SAF SARA-2.1) and generated power as the percentage of the installed capacity (based on OPSD) for solar energy for Germany in 2015 (including PV module orientations). The red (orange) line represents the regression line of corrected (uncorrected) solar data. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

production time series from 1995 to 2015. To get an overview of the amount of the produced energy in Germany the annual sum of solar and wind production is shown for the whole time series in Fig. 8. The mean generated energy is 102 TWh per year assuming a fixed installed capacity of 38 GW for solar and 40 GW for wind power representing the situation in 2015 [27]. The simulated produced energy in 2015 (110 TWh) fits well with OPSD (112 TWh - OPSD [27]). Extremely warm summers with high solar irradiance are clearly recognisable in Fig. 8, i.e., 2003, with the highest sum of solar energy generation (37 TWh) in that time series. On the contrary, 2003 had the lowest annual wind energy production (61.7 TWh) which leads to an overall annual energy production of 99 TWh, which is slightly less than the average 102 TWh. The maximum wind energy production (81.1 TWh) occurred in 1998, the same year with the overall lowest solar energy production (29.7 TWh). The year with the highest total energy production was in 2007 with 112.2 TWh, whereas the lowest total energy production was in 1996 with 92.3 TWh. The mean energy production is 32.9 TWh for solar and 70.3 TWh for wind energy per year. On average there is about twice as much energy production due to wind compared to solar. Zeng et al. [66] found a global increase in wind speed over land since 2010, leading to increasing wind energy production, whereas in our study the wind energy production shows no distinctive trend in the period 1995–2015 in Germany.

Fig. 9 shows the mean monthly energy production from 1995 to 2015. The wind power dominates in fall and winter, whereas solar and wind power have an equal share in summer. The annual cycle of the contributions from wind and solar to the energy generation is driven by the wind speed and the available solar radiation. While the annual cycle of solar radiation is mainly driven by the astronomical solar cycle with shorter-term variability (on a day-to-day basis) due to the cloud coverage, the annual cycle of the wind speed is driven by meteorological constrains, resulting in substantially larger wind speeds in winter compared to summer. In the winter months the total energy production is slightly higher than in summer, with a maximum production of 9.6 TWh in March and a minimum production (7.7 TWh) in September. The maximum solar energy production is in July (4.4 TWh) and the minimum

Fig. 5. Correlation of the hourly simulated CFs (based on COSMO-REA6) and generated power as the percentage of the installed capacity (based on OPSD) for wind energy for Germany in 2015. The blue (light blue) line represents the correlation line of corrected (uncorrected) wind data. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

production in December with 0.8 TWh as expected due to the solar cycle. Whereas the wind energy production has an opposite annual cycle with highest output in January (8.7 TWh) and lowest in August (3.8 TWh).

The mean annual cycle of the combined solar and wind energy production (Fig. 10) based on daily sums shows a relatively constant energy production throughout the year. The mean daily energy production varies between 187 and 363 GWh, but some shortfall days can be identified in fall and winter with less than 50 GWh daily production, which are of particular interest. It is interesting to note that the minimum daily energy production is much higher in summer (about 100 GWh) than in winter due to the relevant generation of solar energy from radiation in summer even under

Climatological Wind Capacity Factor Germany, 1995 - 2015

Fig. 7. Climatological wind capacity factor (1995–2015) based on COSMO-REA6 hourly wind speed data.

cloudy conditions.

Generally the mean daily wind energy production (up to 700 GWh) is higher than the mean daily solar energy production (up to 225 GWh), but wind energy is more variable, especially in fall and winter compared to solar energy. Bett and Thornton [12] also show, that the day-to-day variability in total power is always reduced by incorporating solar energy.

4.3. Impact of Grosswetterlagen

To further analyse the meteorological situations associated with shortfall days, a “Grosswetterlagen” (GWL) classification is used [54]. The GWL are large-scale weather patterns over Europe and are

Climatological Solar Capacity Factor Germany, 1995 - 2015

Fig. 6. Climatological solar capacity factor (1995–2015) based on SARAH-2.1 30-min SIS and SID data.

Annual Simulated Energy Production 1995-2015, Germany

Fig. 8. Annual simulated energy production [TWh] in Germany (1995–2015, with fixed installed capacity of 2015); red: solar energy, blue: wind energy. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. Mean monthly simulated energy production [TWh] in Germany (1995–2015, with fixed installed capacity of 2015); red: solar energy, blue: wind energy. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

therefore appropriate to study the energy production due to solar radiation and wind speed.

As indicated in Section 4.2 and Fig. 10 the shortfall days occur only in winter, because the solar energy generated, even under cloudy situations, is sufficient to prevent shortfall events (based on the present definition) in summer. Fig. 11 shows the simulated daily generated power per GWL in Germany from 1995 to 2015 considering only the winter month (October to March). Here, it is possible to identify the GWL for shortfall days climatologically. There is a clear dependency of energy production on GWL on a daily basis. The solar energy production is quite low in winter with the exception of a few GWL (e.g. GWL 22). The GWL which cause the lowest total energy production is GWL 9 (“High over Central Europe”), GWL 11 (“Low (Cut-Off) over Central Europe”), GWL 12 (“Anticyclonic Northerly”), GWL 14 (“Icelandic High, Ridge Central Europe”) and GWL 16 (“High over the British Isles”) when also wind

Fig. 10. Annual cycle of the daily sum of solar and wind energy production [GWh] from 1995 to 2015 with the maximum values in red, the minima in blue, the mean daily sum of wind and solar energy production as the black line and the grey shading represents the values between the first and third quantile. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

energy production is low. GWL 15 (“Icelandic High, Trough Central Europe”) could also provide a shortfall day, but has a wide range of possible wind energy production. GWL 9 can already be identified as a possibly critical GWL, since the wind energy generation is comparably low under these situations (Table 3); on average the solar energy generation, however, is able to balance the low wind energy production, but there are instances (i.e., under cloudy situations) when the solar energy production is also comparably low. In Section 4.5 the meteorological situation during GWL 9 will be discussed in detail.

4.4. Shortfall events

The previous analysis focused on daily energy production. To analyse difficult situations for the energy system, longer periods of very low energy production are identified in the next step. These specific time periods with low occurrence of solar and wind energy are called shortfall events. To get an overview of the energy production depending on the event lengths, the variation of the intervals is analysed.

The 21 years of produced solar and wind energy data with hourly values are used for calculating rolling sums with different event lengths (24 h, 48 h, 60 h, 72 h, 96 h and 120 h). The 10 and 20 lowest events for each event length for the total time series are taken into account for further analysis.

Another interesting aspect is the appearance of the shortfall event throughout the year (Fig. 12). All shortfall events occur in fall and winter independent on the event length, mostly in January with 7 and 8 events out of 20. This agrees with the analysis in Fig. 10 also on a daily basis.

Fig. 13 shows the frequency of the individual GWL during shortfall events with a length of 120 h (i.e., 5 days). Here, the 20 events with lowest energy production from 1995 to 2015 are assumed to be appropriate to be further analysed. The distribution of the frequency per GWL is similar for each event length except for the 24 h event length. GWL 9 (“High over Central Europe”) is the most frequent GWL, with about 30% of all events (6 from 20).

Grams et al. [25] also studied low energy output due to wind power in Europe and employed a reduced classification of seven weather regimes composed of blocked and cyclonic regimes. Their analysis focuses only on winter days. They show that weather regimes give a meteorological explanation for fluctuations in wind power in Europe. The weather regime “European blocking” (EuBL) provides the lowest wind CF for Germany (about 10%), because of the negative wind speed anomaly. This weather pattern is comparable to the one associated with GWL 9 identified in Fig. 13.

The meteorological reasons of minimal energy production play an important role in the analysis of electrical power supply. Based on the 120 h rolling sums of simulated solar and wind energy, the 10 events of lowest energy production are listed in Table 4 with the associated GWL classification. The columns on the right-hand side of the table show the produced energy in GWh for solar, wind and the sum of both. Each energy source is divided into the amount of produced energy during the event and the production relative to the mean. The most common GWL sequence (3 of 10 events) associated with shortfall events is GWL 9 followed by GWL 5 (see Table 4, column 3 and 4), which means a high pressure system over central Europe (GWL 9) drifting to the south east (GWL 5). This is also seen in Fig. 13. Only 20%–28% of the mean event energy production is produced during the 120 h events.

4.5. Analysis of a shortfall event at GWL 9

Composite plots of wind speed and cloud cover anomalies (valid for the winter month) for each GWL are used to analyse the

Fig. 11. Simulated solar (red) and wind (blue) energy production [GWh] depending on GWL in Germany from 1995 to 2015 based on daily sums considering only the winter months (October to March). The box represents the mean 50% of the data (interquartile range). The horizontal line inside the box represents the median. The lines extending vertically from the box show 1.5 times the interquartile range of all data. The points represent outliers of the data. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

shortfall events. The composite plots are based on the 10 m-wind speed and the cloud cover from ERA-Interim and their anomalies were calculated in relation to a climate reference period from 1979 to 2018. Figs. 14 and 15 represent the pressure system at GWL 9 which was present the full 120 h event from 22 to 27.12.2006 (Table 4) and will be further analysed. Fig. 15 shows a negative wind speed anomaly in m/s for GWL 9 in winter, which explains the low wind energy production (only 17.2% of the hourly mean) during this event. Fig. 14 shows a negative cloud cover anomaly over Germany during GWL 9 in winter. This means more sunshine which leads to a higher solar CF. During the event 29.3% of the climatological mean solar energy is produced. This is twice the solar energy production during the lowest energy production event in January 1997 (Table 4), nevertheless the solar energy cannot balance the low wind energy production at this event.

4.6. European balancing effects

This subsection is focussing on possible balancing effects during the shortfall events in Germany by other European countries. For this the EMHIREs dataset [38,51], which provides solar and wind CFs for 28 European countries, is used for further analysis. Possible balancing effects are shown particularly for the second lowest 120 h energy production event and its corresponding GWL with a spatial European distribution of the solar and wind CFs. The use of CF is appropriate here, because the energy potential of a country is

Table 3

Overview of the frequency of low energy production GWL in winter and the corresponding amount of daily energy produced. Column 1 and 2 represent the number and name of the GWL classification. The frequency of GWL considering all winter days (October to March) from 1995 to 2015 is shown in column 3. Column 4 and 5 represent the range of daily solar and wind energy production [GWh] during the GWL, which also include the outliers and the last two columns show the corresponding median [GWh].

GWL		Sum of GWL in winter [days]	Daily energy range [GWh] (and Median)	
Name	Number		Solar	Wind
High over Central Europe	9	207	8 - 190 (60)	3 - 352 (74)
Low (Cut-Off) over Central Europe	11	53	10 - 67 (26)	21 - 360 (115)
Anticyclonic Northerly	12	29	13 - 105 (35)	18 - 282 (81)
Icelandic High, Ridge Central Europe	14	64	7 - 137 (38)	13 - 326 (83)
High over the British Isles	16	115	8 - 171 (47)	14 - 306 (93)
Icelandic High, Trough Central Europe	15	21	11 - 116 (30)	21 - 420 (136)

Fig. 12. Number of shortfall events per month from 1995 to 2015 in Germany with event length of 24 h, 48 h, 60 h, 72 h, 96 h and 120 h considering the 20 lowest energy production events for each event length.

Frequency of GWL 1995-2015 on Shortfall Events (120h)

Fig. 13. Frequency of GWL considering the 20 lowest energy production events during 1995–2015 with 120 h event length.

relevant for this analysis (instead of the actual generated power).

Figs. 16 and 17 show the mean wind and solar CFs considering all events associated with GWL 9 in winter. European countries with high wind CFs during GWL 9 are Scandinavia (26–33%), Croatia (31%), Slovenia (26%) and Greece (34%) which could help balancing the low wind CF of 9% in Germany. This can already be assumed on the basis of the pressure system in Figs. 14 and 15, which show a high pressure gradient for the northern part of Europe. Scandinavia, Croatia and Slovenia are probably close enough to Germany to

interexchange wind energy. Even though the wind energy generation potential is high, these countries had hardly any installed wind capacity (860 MW Norway, 384 MW Croatia and 3 MW Slovenia) in 2015 [27], which is only 2% and less of the installed capacity in Germany in 2015. The solar energy potential is generally quite low in winter. European countries with high solar CFs during GWL 9 periods are mainly located in southern Europe, i.e. Portugal and Spain.

5. Summary and conclusions

The aim of this work was to study the climatological relationship between the potential of solar and the potential of wind energy during the time period 1995 to 2015 in Germany, to determine low energy production events, so-called shortfall events, and to identify related “Grosswetterlagen” (GWL). Two datasets with high spatial and temporal resolution have been used to calculate climatological CFs for wind (COSMO-REA6) and solar (CM SAF SARAH-2.1, COSMO-REA6) energy in Germany.

To reproduce the measured power production in 2015 based on Open Power System Data (OPSD), the approach of an angle distribution of PV installation, using an inclination angle of 20.6° and a southward orientation, was assumed (based on the work of Saint-Drenan et al. [55,56]). Even though their correlation was high, the simulated CFs overestimated the actual CF for solar and wind energy. The reasons for the overestimation might be, that some effects, like transmission losses, contamination effects (due to dust or snow on solar panels [62]), shading by surrounding obstacles or the shutdown of windplants in case of too high wind speeds or power deficits due to turbine wakes [63,64] are not considered in the calculation. The calibration of the simulated data with Open Power System Data (OPSD) to get generated energy is important to perform a reasonable climatological analysis of the potential of solar and wind energy. A linear fit of the simulated and actual CFs based on 2015 (as seen in Figs. 4 and 5) is appropriate to correct the simulated CFs [55] for 2015 and is applied to all other years considered.

The climatological mean solar CF varies between 10% and 14% (Fig. 6) and the wind CF between 5% and 50% (Fig. 7) in Germany. The highest wind CFs are found at offshore regions in the North and Baltic Sea. On average a regional balancing effect is seen in southern Germany, where higher solar CFs can balance low wind CFs, while in northern parts high wind CFs can balance low solar CFs, which agrees with the results of Kaspar et al. [5] where the same structure was demonstrated. Henckes et al. [67] also found that Germany and

Fig. 14. Cloud cover anomaly at GWL 9 in winter based on ERA-Interim. The contour interval is 4%, where grey symbolizes positive and orange/violett negative anomalies. Also shown is the mean sea-level pressure (MSLP) with a contour interval of 3 hPa. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Europe have significant balancing effects focussing on wind energy and the proper choice of an electricity transmission can be highly relevant.

The CF represents the potential of energy production due to solar and wind energy, but not the actual generated energy production, which is relevant for time series analysis and identifying shortfall events. For this reason the simulated CFs were converted into generated energy by multiplication with the installed solar (38 GW) and wind (40 GW) capacity from 2015 based on OPSD. The time series shows that about two third of renewable energy production in Germany is due to wind power (Fig. 8). In winter the produced wind energy is higher, whereas in summer solar and wind energy have an equal share (Fig. 9). Wind energy is highly variable, especially in winter, whereas solar energy is rather predictable due to the annual solar cycle. Furthermore, the mean annual solar and wind energy production indicates a slightly annual anticorrelation, i.e., solar and wind energy compensate each

Table 4

The 10 lowest 120 h events with simulated production of electrical power from solar and wind from 1995 to 2015. The first columns state start and end of an event. The 3rd and 4th column represent the number and abbreviation of the GWL classification and in brackets the number of days the GWL occurred. The 6 following columns describe the produced solar, wind and the sum of solar and wind energy at the whole event in GWh and the production relative to the mean (1995–2015). The last row represents the climatological mean energy production for a 5 day period for solar, wind and its sum.

Event Start	Event End	GWL classification		Produced Energy [GWh]					
		Number	Name (# days)	Solar		Wind		Sum	
				Event	% of mean	Event	% of mean	Event	% of mean
1997-01-05	1997-01-10	16,14	HB (2.5), HNA (2.5)	68.5	15.1	226.5	23.5	295.0	20.8
2006-12-22	2006-12-27	9	HM (5)	132.8	29.3	165.6	17.2	298.4	21.1
2015-10-16	2015-10-21	11,12,10	TM (1.5), NA (3), BM (0.5)	150.0	33.0	161.5	16.8	311.5	22.0
1996-12-07	1996-12-12	24	SEA (5)	89.0	19.6	238.8	24.8	327.7	23.1
2002-01-06	2002-01-11	9,5	HM (4), SWA(1)	79.6	17.5	270.3	28.1	349.9	24.7
1996-11-13	1996-11-18	11,27,29	TM (1.5), SZ (2), TRW (1)	99.0	21.8	255.3	26.5	354.4	25.0
2015-01-18	2015-01-23	25,17	SEZ (4), TRM (1)	125.8	27.7	229.3	23.8	355.0	25.1
1995-10-12	1995-10-17	26,9,5	SA (1), HM (2), SWA (2)	231.7	51.0	128.1	13.3	359.7	25.4
2007-12-17	2007-12-22	9,5	HM (4), SWA (1)	225.8	49.7	134.7	14.0	360.5	25.5
2003-01-06	2003-01-11	14,12	HNA (3), NA (2)	124.3	27.4	274.2	28.5	396.9	28.0
1995	2015			454.0	100	962.9	100	1416.5	100

Fig. 15. Wind speed anomaly at GWL 9 in winter based on ERA-Interim. The contour interval is 0.5 m/s, where blue represents a negative anomaly and orange/red a positive anomaly. Also shown is the mean sea-level pressure (MSLP) with a contour interval of 3 hPa. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Mean Solar Capacity Factors
GWL 9

Fig. 17. Mean solar CFs [%] averaged over all GWL 9 in winter.

Mean Wind Capacity Factors
GWL 9

Fig. 16. Mean wind CFs [%] averaged over all GWL 9 in winter.

other on the annual cycle considering average energy production (Fig. 10), also found by Kaspar et al. [5]. Some studies on climate change scenarios (Regional Climate Projection (RCP) 4.5) in near future decades [68,69] show a decrease in wind speed for large parts of Europe which might influence wind energy production. On the other hand indicates Zeng et al. [66] a positive trend for wind speed since 2010 on a global scale based on surface data and global climate model simulations. Projected changes in the surface irradiance and PV solar energy production are small and differ in sign

between regional (decrease) and global (increase) climate model simulations [1].

Some particular days were identified with very low energy production for both, solar and wind energy, which might likely be compensated with short-term storage capabilities, such as batteries [17]. A challenge for the energy supply are longer periods of low energy production, because of less energy storage possibilities. Therefore the dataset of hourly solar and wind energy production is used to calculate the energy production for different event lengths (24 h, 48 h, 60 h, 72 h, 96 h, 120 h). With our definition of a low energy production event, a shortfall event only occurs in winter (Fig. 12).

The meteorological conditions leading to shortfall events are analysed with the help of the “Grosswetterlagen” (GWL) classification of [54] which provides information of the weather patterns over Europe. A clear dependency of generated solar and wind energy on the GWL is found (Fig. 11). Shortfall events with only about 20% of the mean daily energy production (Table 4) corresponds mostly to GWL 9, “High over Central Europe” (Fig. 13), which can be well explained with the composite plots of wind speed and cloud cover anomaly (Figs. 14 and 15).

The investigation of possible balancing effects by other European countries during a shortfall event in Germany is relevant in a European-wide connected electricity network. The simulated European solar and wind CFs are based on the EMHIREs dataset (provided by JRC). European countries which have high potential to balance shortfall events in Germany at GWL 9 are Scandinavia, Slovenia and Croatia, where a higher pressure gradient is leading to high wind CF (Figs. 16 and 17). This study shows the high potential of an European energy system, to compensate shortfall events in Germany with the help of other European countries. Combining solar and wind energy with other renewable energy sources, i.e., hydropower [17], can also reduce the negative effects of shortfall events. However, the increasing need for energy transition also in transport and heating sector has to be considered, wherefore further renewable energy studies and also storage research is needed.

The methods developed in this work are applicable to other regions of the world, especially the analysis of meteorological fluctuations and the resulting potential of solar and wind energy. This could support the expansion of the energy system relying on renewable energies, or for countries which plan to expand their renewable energy network.

This work has identified the meteorological factors associated with problematic energy production days and events in Germany and provides hints for a possible future European-wide energy system design and necessary energy storage capabilities for the compensation of shortfall events.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jaqueline Drücke: Writing - original draft, Validation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Software. **Michael Borsche:** Writing - original draft, Data curation. **Paul James:** Writing - original draft, Data curation, Visualization. **Frank Kaspar:** Writing - review & editing, Methodology. **Uwe Pfeifroth:** Writing - original draft, Software, Data curation. **Bodo Ahrens:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Conceptualization. **Jörg Trentmann:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Conceptualization, Methodology, Software.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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